

COMPUTER SCIENCES

A MULTIFACTORIAL APPROACH TO THE ANALYSIS OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS' EFFECTIVENESS

Sesadze V.

*Doctor of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Faculty of Informatics and Management Systems,
Georgian Technical University,
Tbilisi, Georgia
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3239-2225>*

Imnadze E.

*Doctoral Student at the Faculty of Natural Sciences,
Mathematics, Technology and Pharmacy,
Sokhumi State University,
Tbilisi, Georgia
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3869-0895>*

Kereselidze N.

*PhD, Associate Professor,
at the Faculty of Natural Sciences,
Mathematics, Technology and Pharmacy,
Sokhumi State University,
Tbilisi, Georgia,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3363-8310>*

Abstract

In the modern educational system, the assessment and prediction of the performance of higher education institutions (HEIs) are closely linked to multifactorial parameters such as students' academic achievements, the competence of instructors, infrastructural resources, and the effectiveness of management. Traditional qualitative approaches often fail to capture the complex interactions among these components, which necessitates the use of computational and mathematical models, as well as the implementation of such a model using the Maple symbolic mathematics software package.

The aim of the article is to develop a mathematical and computational model for achieving success in higher education institutions, a model based on multifactor analysis that integrates student-related, academic, infrastructural, and managerial components. The proposed model provides an objective, data-driven assessment, determines the weights of the indicators, and offers predictive capability. The results obtained may be used both to improve the quality of education and for strategic management processes, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of higher education institutions in the contemporary educational environment.

Keywords: computational model; mathematical model; linear functions; factors influencing the educational process, Maple - symbolic mathematics package.

Introduction.

Education and intellect represent core values in the 21st century—a century defined by knowledge. Education and professional expertise determine the economic strength of a country.

The modern educational space is developing dynamically and requires approaches that ensure systematic analysis and prediction of the success of higher education institutions. The factors determining this success are multifaceted and include both academic achievements and pedagogical competencies, organizational and infrastructural resources and the effectiveness of management. The complex interconnection of these factors requires a scientifically grounded, objective, and quantitative assessment, which is difficult to achieve only by using traditional methods based solely on qualitative evaluation.

In this context, the use of mathematical and computational modeling becomes particularly significant, as it enables the identification of success indicators, the determination of their influence, and the

forecasting of the development of educational institutions [1-2], [4-5]. Mathematical and computational models are a solid foundation for optimizing managerial decisions, improving the quality of education, and effectively implementing strategic management processes.

In Western and international practice, various mathematical and computational models and algorithms are employed to optimize the assignment of teachers to positions. These methods include classical and modified Hungarian algorithms, evolutionary algorithms, and multi-objective optimization techniques. The Hungarian method and its variations are commonly applied to teacher–position assignment problems, as reflected in the research of N. Ibrahim (2024). In Romania, at the Technical University of Bucharest, the system developed by Francis Diallo (2024) relies on evolutionary algorithms and multi-objective optimization to refine instructional activity schedules, with the goal of maximizing teachers' preferences and ensuring a more effective and equitable

distribution. Similarly, at the University of Edinburgh in the United Kingdom, an integer programming model has been applied—using the example of the School of Mathematics—to optimize teacher appointments while prioritizing the maximization of teachers' preferences for fair and efficient allocation.

The aim of the given article is the formulation of mathematical and computational models for achieving success in a higher educational institution and the demonstration of their theoretical-practical significance. These models will be based on multifactor analysis, that affects key aspects of educational process management. The article also presents the implementation of the mathematical model using the Maple symbolic mathematics package. This approach enables both researchers and administrators to objectively assess the current situation and identify optimal directions for development.

Main part. In modern literature, the performance of an educational institution is regarded as a complex concept encompassing academic, organizational, social, and infrastructural components. Assessing these components presents a significant challenge, as they are closely interrelated and form a complex system. Research by Tinto (1993) and Astin (1999) demonstrates that student success is directly linked to the quality of the educational environment and the level of institutional support. Furthermore, UNESCO's 2021 report emphasizes that institutional effectiveness should be evaluated not only through academic indicators but also with consideration of socio-economic and cultural contexts.

Mathematical and computational models are widely used in educational research because they provide a data-driven foundation for analysis. Among these models, the following are particularly noteworthy:

- **Statistical models:** Pascarella and Terenzini (2005) indicate that regression analysis is effective for studying the influence of social and academic factors on students' achievements [7].
- **Optimization models:** Johnes (2006) emphasizes that linear programming is useful for optimizing resource allocation in universities [8].
- **Stochastic models:** Bean and Metzner (1985) employed Markov chains to predict student dropout [9].
- **Multifactor indices:** QS (Quacquarelli Symonds) and THE (Times Higher Education) are two leading global rankings that evaluate universities based on multiple criteria, including academic reputation, research quality, and lecturer-to-student ratio, although their methodologies and results differ slightly. The QS ranking focuses on academic reputation, citations, and internationalization, whereas **THE ranking** uses a more complex methodology, giving greater weight to teaching quality, research activity, and international relations.

Many studies have been dedicated to evaluating the performance of educational organizations. For example, OECD's *Education at a Glance* (2023) highlights the need for systemic indicators to assess the quality of education [10].

Hanushek and Woessmann (2015) emphasize that mathematical and statistical modeling is critical for analyzing the relationship between education quality and economic growth [11].

As for our country, Georgia, the National Center for Educational Quality Enhancement (EQE, 2019) uses multifactor evaluation models during the accreditation of higher education institutions (HEIs) [12].

The analysis of these studies indicates that the assessment of success cannot be limited to only one indicator. A comprehensive mathematical model is required, which simultaneously takes into consideration both academic and managerial parameters. Precisely This approach provides the foundation for a systematic and predictable evaluation.

Four main factors affecting the teaching process are discussed in the work [3]; these are:

1. "Discipline factor" – this encompasses positive and negative behaviors, the students' personal attitudes, behaviors and habits, and adherence to rules of conduct in the learning environment. It also considers extreme or unregulated behaviors and the presence and management of necessary sanctions. As the disciplinary function increases, it continues to grow simultaneously, $t = t_1$, the function can eventually take negative values:

$$f(t) = -a_1 t - b_1$$

The maximal point, where the disciplinary value of the transition from normal discipline to extreme discipline is expressed $t = t_j = t_{max}$. Accordingly,

when $t = t_j \in [0, t_v]$ we have:

$$\max(f(t_{max})) = a_1 t_{max} + b_1 = c_1$$

where $c_1 \in \mathbb{R}$

2. "Teacher factor" – the qualification of teachers, experience, and the use of innovative teaching methods.

This is because, in the interval $(0, m)$ each teacher is expected to have the opportunity to perform at their maximum potential. Accordingly, the maximum value of this factor can be expressed as:

$$\max(g(t_{max})) = a_2 t_{max} + b_2 = m$$

$m \in \mathbb{R}$. Maximum point $t = t_j = t_{max}$, when $t = t_j \in [0, t_v]$

3. "Student factor" – this factor includes attendance, learning motivation, average assessment score, course-completion rate. Taking into account the student's contribution, the maximum value of the educational institution's success will take the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \max(S(t)) &= e^{\frac{(\max(\varphi(t))(\max(f(t))(\max(g(t))^{(t-t_0)}))}{\min h(t)}} S_0 \\ &= e^{\frac{rc_1 m}{1} (t-t_0)} S_0 = \\ &= e^{rc_1 m (t-t_0)} S_0. \end{aligned}$$

Here, $S(t)$ and $\max(s(t))$, $t_0 = 0$ in the time interval $[0, t_v]$

If $S(t) = S_0$ and $0 < S(t) < 1$ then this is an unsuccessful situation, and in that case, the interval $(t - t_0)$

Should be taken in the form of $t_{j+1} - t_j$

4. "Negative Factor" – this factor reflects the influence of the family environment or economic conditions, which negatively affects the student's work,

$$\text{solve}\left(\left\{a \cdot (t1)^2 + b \cdot (t1) + c = dt1, a \cdot (t2)^2 + b \cdot t2 + c = dt2, a \cdot (t3)^2 + b \cdot t3 + c = dt3\right\}, \{a, b, c\}\right)$$

$$a = \frac{dt1t2 - dt1t3 - dt2t1 + dt2t3 + dt3t1 - dt3t2}{t1^2t2 - t1^2t3 - t1t2^2 + t1t3^2 + t2^2t3 - t2t3^2},$$

$$b = -\frac{dt1t2^2 - dt1t3^2 - dt2t1^2 + dt2t3^2 + dt3t1^2 - dt3t2^2}{(t1 - t2)(t1t2 - t1t3 - t2t3 + t3^2)},$$

$$c = \frac{dt1t2^2t3 - dt1t2t3^2 - dt2t1^2t3 + dt2t1t3^2 + dt3t1^2t2 - dt3t1t2^2}{(t1 - t2)(t1t2 - t1t3 - t2t3 + t3^2)}$$

Fig. Solution of system in the Maple software package.

Based on the program results, the disciplinary situation can be determined at the time point $t = t_j$ using the corresponding disciplinary function. The analysis showed that considering the combined effect of various factors provides a more objective assessment of the successful performance of an educational institution.

Conclusion

The computer and mathematical models discussed employ functions representing “disciplinary factors,” “teacher performance factors,” “student factors,” and “negative factors” to determine actual outcomes. When the success value is negative, it becomes possible to identify and improve specific functions that adversely affect the results. For example, in cases of disciplinary failure, the function can be adjusted using average values and disciplinary indicators to construct a linear equation for subsequent stages.

The model is also used to achieve positive outcomes through carefully selected functions, particularly when the management of an educational institution is assessed negatively. A multi-factorial approach ensures that development is informed by comprehensive data, enhancing effectiveness, reducing the risk of subjectivity, and strengthening the accuracy of the analytical process.

Applying a multi-factorial approach in the accreditation of educational institutions allows for an objective and multifaceted assessment of educational quality. Considering only a single criterion cannot capture the overall picture of the system, whereas a combined analysis of factors reveals the full spectrum of strengths and weaknesses.

Thus, this model represents a crucial mechanism in the management of educational quality. Its further refinement, through the integration of modern analytical tools and databases, ensures that higher education in Georgia remains competitive within the international educational landscape.

References

1. R. S. S. Junior, Applications of mathematical modeling to study the population growth of Sergipe, *International Journal of Educational Studies*, 1(3), (2014) 119-123.
2. I. Raza, Factors affecting adoption of educational discipline and satisfaction level among higher education students, *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 3(1), (2016) 100-122.
3. Mustafa Kandemir, A Mathematical modelling of success in education, *Journal of New Results in Science* 10(1) (2021) 10-23, https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/jnrs/article/901756?issue_id=62194
4. V. I. Agoshkov, J. P. Puel, *Mathematical models of life support systems*, Volume I, Oxford, United Kingdom, 2009.
5. M. F. Brillhante, M. I. Gomes, D. Pestana, Extensions of Verhulst model in population dynamics and extremes, *Chaotic Modeling and Simulation*, 4, (2012) 575-591.
6. G. Chikadze, V. Sesadze. *Mathematics on the Computer*. A Supplementary Textbook (Second Edition). 2021. p. 296. ISBN 9789941-8-3533-9 IT-Consulting scientific center of GTU, 2021
7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/307726804_Pascarella_T_and_Terenzin_P_2005_How_College_Affects_Students_A_Third_decade_of_Research_2nd_ed_San_Francisco_Jossey-Bass
8. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272166409_JONES_S_2006_A_Tale_of_Two_Literacies_Girls_growing_up_biculturally_literate_in_two_UK_communities_In_HICKEY_T_ed_Language_Learning_and_Literacy_RAI_99-113
9. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=989094>
10. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/education-at-a-glance-2023_e13bef63-en.html
11. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345888473_The_Knowledge_Capital_of_Nations_Education_and_the_Economics_of_Growth
12. <https://eqe.ge/ka/page/static/811/umaghlesi-ganatilebis-khariskhis-ganvitarebis-damoukidebeli-saagtoebis-evropuli-reestri-eqar>